

Decarboxylation of Benzylmalonic Acid in Resorcinol and Catechol

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The decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid was studied at five temperatures in resorcinol and catechol. The reaction is first order in both the solvents. The observations support the view that the decomposition proceeds through an intermediate complex.

CLARK¹ has studied the decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid in the molten state as well as in many polar solvents and in cresol. He has suggested a correlation between the isokinetic temperature and the melting point of the reactant. Peterson *et al.*² have critically analyzed the problem of validity of enthalpy entropy of activation relationship. The decarboxylation of oxalic acid³ was studied in resorcinol and catechol, the plot of enthalpy-entropy of activation resulted in a fair straight line when the data of the other solvents were taken in plotting the graphs. The decarboxylation of malonic acid⁴, benzoic acid⁵ and substituted benzoic acids⁶ have been studied in resorcinol and catechol. It was found necessary to study the derivatives of malonic acid in resorcinol and catechol to know whether it follows the same mechanism as followed by malonic acid or not. The kinetics of the decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid in resorcinol and catechol was studied and the results are reported herein.

Experimental

Reagent: Benzylmalonic acid Analar grade, m.p. = 120.2° was used without further purification. White crystalline solids of resorcinol and catechol (Analar grade) were used as solvents. The colour of the molten solvent was found to be dark red.

Procedure: The progress of the reaction was studied by measuring the volume of carbon dioxide evolved. The experimental set up and the procedure is the same as described in our previous articles^{7,8}. About 50 g resorcinol and 50 g catechol were separately taken in each run and 0.3489 g sample of benzylmalonic acid was introduced in the usual manner into the reactor. On complete decarboxylation, the acid produced 40.0 ml of carbon dioxide at STP. The whole set up was placed in an oil-bath ± 0.05 . The CO₂ was collected at room temperature in a measuring burette which had been previously saturated with carbon dioxide. Duplicate runs were made and the deviation in the results were 0.23-0.41%.

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In every experiment the plot of $\log (V_{\infty} - V_t)$ vs. t was linear indicating that the reaction is first order where V_{∞} is the volume of CO₂ after complete decomposition and V_t is the volume at time t . The average rate constants calculated from the slopes of the logarithmic plots are tabulated in Table 1. The activation parameters, based upon the data in Table 1, are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—APPARENT FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE DECARBOXYLATION OF BENZYLMAONIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

Temp. °C	Resorcinol $k_1(\text{sec}^{-1}) \times 10^5$	Catechol $k_1(\text{sec}^{-1}) \times 10^5$
120	9.33	10.23
125	10.09	14.79
130	23.99	21.88
140	56.23	43.65
150	131.80	87.10

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR BENZYLMAONIC ACID IN RESORCINOL AND CATECHOL

Solvents	E kcal/ mole	$\log A$ (sec^{-1})	$\Delta F^\ddagger$ kcal/ mole	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kcal/ mole	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ cal deg ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
Resorcinol	28.32	11.79 ± 0.02	30.34 ± 0.03	27.52 ± 0.02	- 5.66 ± 0.03
Catechol	23.16	8.87 ± 0.01	30.65 ± 0.02	22.36 ± 0.03	-18.59 ± 0.02

Av. $k_1(\text{sec}^{-1}) \times 10^5$ at 140° in resorcinol is 56.2 and in catechol 43.65.

Discussion

The decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid is kinetically first order at the run temperatures of this investigation. The rate determining step is an intermediate complex between benzylmalonic acid and resorcinol. The energy of activation is 28.32 kcal mole⁻¹ which is very close to 27.33 kcal mole⁻¹ reported by Clark in phenol. This indicates that a

single hydroxyl group of resorcinol is associated with the solute like phenol and the other hydroxyl group is in the isolated form and the distribution of energy among the bonds of activated complex is exactly similar to that of phenol. Though resorcinol is more acidic in nature than phenol and catechol is more acidic than resorcinol, the rate of decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid is faster in phenol than in resorcinol and faster in resorcinol than in catechol. Similar observations have been reported for the decarboxylation of malonic acid³ and oxalic acid⁴ in these solvents. It has been reported earlier that the hydroxyl group of phenol¹¹ is associated with malonic acid, since phenol, resorcinol and catechol have similar structures, one can expect similar association in the case of benzylmalonic acid in these solvents.

The results of Table I shows that the rate of decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid at lower temperatures are faster in catechol than in resorcinol. This indicates that the two adjacent hydroxyl groups of catechol associates with benzylmalonic acid at higher temperatures and at lower temperatures single hydroxyl group associates, hence the lower rates in resorcinol. This behaviour is similar to that of oxanilic acid¹⁰ in resorcinol and catechol.

The entropy of activation for the decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid in catechol is more negative than in resorcinol which may be attributed to the fact that the intermediate complex in catechol is bulkier than in resorcinol. The higher steric factor in resorcinol shows that the reaction is more disordered than in catechol.

The entropy and enthalpy of activation for the decarboxylation of benzylmalonic acid in several

other solvents¹ are similar to the values obtained by us in this work. The enthalpy-entropy of activation plot gave a straight line. The isokinetic temperature reported by Clark is 393 K° corresponding to a temperature 120.2° which is very close to the melting point of benzylmalonic acid. Our results also support the conclusion arrived at by Clark.

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